

Integrating Generative AI into Game Development Pipelines: A User-centred Approach to Creative Efficiency

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Abstract

In an era shaped by the growing influence of Artificial Intelligence (AI), this thesis examines the role of Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI), an emerging technology that is transforming multiple industries.

The study aims to analyse the characteristics of GenAI and its capacity to reshape creative processes. Specifically, the research focuses on the video game industry and investigates how AI-generated images are incorporated into game development pipelines. It explores the use of GenAI, with an emphasis on Stable Diffusion (SD) models, within production workflows and assesses their interaction with artistic processes. By evaluating the integration of GenAI into design environments, the study measures its effects on creativity, productivity, and the structure of creative workflows.

Keywords: Generative Artificial Intelligence, Stable Diffusion, Game Development, Creative Efficiency, Concept Art, AI-Generated Images, User Interfaces, Integration Challenges, Action Design Research, Human-AI Collaboration, Prompt Engineering, Parameter Tuning

Disclaimer

This master thesis was conducted as part of an academic research project in collaboration with Ubisoft Ancey during the author's internship as a Technical Artist.

Important Clarifications:

- None of the concepts, visual assets, or workflows presented in this thesis are related to any current or past production, intellectual property, or internal strategy of Ubisoft or any of its subsidiaries.
- All generated images and tools were developed solely as part of an independent research effort to explore the creative potential of Generative AI technologies in game development.
- No content produced during this research has been, or will be, used in the commercial development of Ubisoft games.
- Ubisoft Ancey has reviewed and approved the publication of this thesis.

The author assumes full responsibility for the content, findings, and interpretations presented in this work.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Problem statement

In an era where Artificial Intelligence (AI) is redefining the boundaries of creativity, Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) emerges as a game-changer in many industries. Unlike discriminative AI, which only produces predictions, GenAI can generate new content, learning from data without explicit instructions. AI is no longer a task executor but also an innovator. It is an essential tool in creative tasks (e.g., marketing content creation, music production, creating software, designing fashion) [?](Feuerriegel et al., 2023). However, for many, AI seems like a complex black box as generative Machine Learning (ML) models often lack clear interpretability and transparency (Zhu et al., 2018), posing challenges in their adoption and application.

Focusing on the gaming industry, this study explores the integration of AI-generated images into game development pipelines. Specifically, it examines the use of Stable Diffusion (SD) models with the Automatic1111 web user interface (WebUI), (AUTOMATIC1111, 2023). This research focuses on exploring the interaction between artists and GenAI, specifically investigating how GenAI can boost the efficiency and creative capacity of concept artists. By designing workflows and developing simplified user interfaces (UI) to automate these workflows, this thesis explores the potential of GenAI in augmenting creativity, generating diverse artistic ideas, and accelerating the design process. Additionally, it seeks to identify the challenges associated with integrating GenAI into existing systems and to formulate strategies to effectively mitigate these challenges. The aim is to establish a balance where GenAI can be accessible and practical for artists, while reducing the technical barrier and steep learning curve.

In the gaming industry, concept artists are responsible for designing and creating the intended look, style, and visual feel of a game (Nashville Film Institute, 2021). Concept arts then serve as reference for 3D artists. These artists draw key elements like characters, props, weapons, architecture, and environments. Their pre-production work establishes an artistic direction unique to each game, enhancing its immersion and authenticity (Dealessandri, 2021). Drawing detailed concept art can take several days. Concept artists frequently face challenges such as working under tight deadlines, adapting to changing project requirements, maintaining a consistent style while being adaptable, and effectively communicating their ideas to clients and team members. They may also deal with creative blocks, managing feedback and criticism, and staying up to date with new software and technologies (Lilly, 2015). Artists must operate within tight time constraints, as one of the primary challenges in game production is minimizing development delays, which can lead to escalated production costs and may also have repercussions on both the game's reception and the studio's reputation.

This study seeks to answer several research questions (RQ) regarding the integration of AI-generated images into the concept art design process in game development. RQ1 explores whether GenAI can be incorporated into artists' design process. RQ2 examines whether GenAI contributes to increased creativity, serving as a valuable source of inspiration for artists, and if it can enhance efficiency by speeding art creation. Lastly, RQ3 assesses the role of guided workflows and simplified web interfaces as strategies to mitigate GenAI challenging integration in game studios.

While existing implementations of GenAI in gaming, such as Unity Muse or procedural generation tools, focus primarily on high-level asset creation or scripted automation, this study proposes a novel approach grounded in user-centred design. What sets this work apart is integrating a custom, artist-focused interface (ArtistUI) directly informed by the needs and constraints of professional game concept artists. Unlike generalised tools, the workflow and UI developed here are tailored to streamline image generation, reduce cognitive load, and fit seamlessly within creative workflows instead of replacing existing ones. By

combining empirical evaluation with iterative design, this thesis offers not just a tool, but a replicable methodology for embedding GenAI into the early stages of game production in a way that enhances both creativity and efficiency.

1.2. Research objectives

NVIDIA, OpenAI, Microsoft, Amazon, Google, Hugging Face, IMB, and other big tech companies are always aiming to develop faster and more powerful GenAI solutions and break the next boundaries (Wegner, 2023). In the field of image generation, there are continuous new innovations in the field of creative content generation, including text-to-3D (Poole et al., 2022), real-time sketch-to-image (Danamir, 2023), text-to-video (Stability AI, 2023a), etc. GenAI is still a novelty for consumers and businesses, but it will soon find its way into products and processes in a lot of industries, and the gaming industry is no exception. For GenAI to fully integrate into the game development, key factors include strategic planning, understanding, and navigating the complex and evolving landscape of this technology, as well as addressing technical challenges like integrating GenAI into existing game engines and development tools. It is also important to consider talent implications, as GenAI can change the nature of certain roles in game development, requiring new skills and approaches (Christofferson et al., 2023).

This study focuses on the seamless integration of AI-generated images for artists. It aims to design and evaluate a workflow for generating character sheets, comparing the user experience of the open-source WebUI with a simplified, custom-designed UI. The solutions' integration into a game studio are guided by the Action Design Research (ADR) methodology, as described by Sein et al. (2011). This methodology supports continuous development, evaluation, and refinement of IT artifacts, effectively balancing practical and research demands in organisational contexts to address real-world problems while generating valuable research outcomes (Haj-Bolouri et al., 2017). ADR is chosen for its compatibility with practice-inspired research and reciprocal shaping, enabling the creation of a solution that is both deeply embedded and iterative, effectively meeting the specific technological and organisational requirements of implementing GenAI in the video game industry.

The study involves a diverse set of qualitative and quantitative data, including field observation, Qualtrics survey, followed by a semi-structured interview of 6 participants from the gaming industry, including artists among other roles, and individuals with varied levels of experience using AI and generative tools in general. This diverse set of data and participants is expected to provide insights into the effectiveness and usability of the developed solutions, offering a comprehensive understanding of GenAI's impact on the creative process.

In the next parts, we will present an overview of GenAI, and the model and platform used for image generation in this study. We will cover the technical requirements for replicating these results, followed by a literature review (refer to Section 2) of AI in video games, text-to-image techniques, GenAI's applications in gaming, and AI's impact on creativity, efficiency, and innovation.

1.3. Document structure

The remainder of the thesis is structured as follows. Section 2 is the literature review on AI applications in games, a state-of-the-art review of text-to-image generation, applications of GenAI in games, then a part on how creativity, efficiency and innovation can be enhanced with AI and specifically GenAI. Section 3 is an introduction to text-to-image techniques using SD WebUI to set some guidelines on what parameters will be used during this research and to better understand the effect of the main parameters on image generation.

The ADR method will be used in Section 4. This methodology is for developing and evaluating Information Technology (IT) artifacts combining Design Science Research (DSR) and Action Research (AR) while considering the organisational context (Sein et al., 2011). It helps develop IT solutions, test them in real-world scenarios, and refine them based on feedback, and is commonly used in the Information Systems (IS) discipline, as it ensures that the tools developed are practical and meet the needs of those using them in a specific industry. The ADR artifacts of the thesis are the GenAI workflow and the UI prototype (the ArtistUI).

Section 5 focuses on the limitations of the generative model (SD) and the solutions developed, the technical, human and ethical limitations, followed by the alternative solutions. Finally, Section 6 concludes this paper and proposes an opening to future work.

1.4. Generative AI and choice of platform

This part presents the technical advancements that have led to the development of GenAI technologies. It includes a detailed description of the SD model, then provides a comparative analysis of various image generation platforms, justifying the use of SD for this study. ML has progressed from its creation in the 1950s, where algorithms were designed to follow a set of rules. By the 1960s, advancements to neural networks led to the development of artificial neural networks (ANNs), making ML a vital component of AI evolution in the late 1970s. This technology was useful for analysing data and enabling machines to make decisions or predictions which involve performing tasks using ML techniques trained on large datasets (Foote, 2021).

GenAI is the subset of AI that can generate new content or data similar to its training data (Gozalo-Brizuela et al., 2023). Its creative capacities were developed with the introduction of the two most popular GenAI models: Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) by Ian Goodfellow (2014), an adversarial process resulting in the continuous improvement of the generated images similar to the training data; alongside Variational Autoencoders (VAEs), an encoder-decoder architecture for generating new data, a leap forward allowing for a new field called Generative Modelling. NVIDIA then made significant development with a new training methodology for GANs (Karras et al., 2017), producing more photorealistic images, improving their quality, stability, and variation. Additionally, Transformers were introduced in the paper "Attention is All You Need" (Vaswani et al., 2017), and their ability to handle sequential data has been crucial for tasks like text generation and language modelling, reducing training data time. Transformers in text-to-image models are used by OpenAI's DALL-E for processing and interpreting textual descriptions (prompts) to guide image generation. It was only in 2020 that GenAI technologies were really put into consumer's hands with the release of Midjourney, Dall-E 2 and the open-source release of Stable Diffusion.

This study focuses on SD, a latent diffusion model (LDM) for generating images from text. Introduced by Stability AI research scientists (Rombach et al., 2021), this image generation model is pre-trained on 2,3 billion English-captioned images from the Internet. LDMs mark a significant step forward in GenAI, offering advantages over Transformers, GANs, and VAEs. They are less costly and complex to pre-train yet deliver high-quality outputs. LDMs are notable for their computational efficiency and effective scaling capabilities. GANs and LDM are both used for generating images but differ in their approaches. GANs have two neural networks competing against each other to produce realistic images, while LDMs involve encoding images and using a process of progressively adding and removing noise in a controlled manner to generate new images. OpenAI researchers discuss guided diffusion and how LDMs better perform than GANs by enhancing efficiency and control in image generation, giving more stable and diverse output (Dhariwal & Nichol, 2021).

Figure 1: Architecture of a Latent Diffusion Model. From "High-Resolution Image Synthesis with Latent Diffusion Models" by Rombach et al., 2021.

Figure 1 illustrates the text-to-image process using LDMs, starting with an image x being converted into a less complex latent representation z via an encoder \mathcal{E} , making the process much faster than operating in the high-dimensional image space. The diffusion process then adds noise over several steps, which a denoising U-Net reverses to produce a clean image. The model uses inputs like text and semantic maps, which link words to their meanings, improving the accuracy of the generated image. By merging data or using targeted attention mechanisms, the model refines its image generation to be more accurate to the descriptions given.

Image generator	Midjourney	DALL-E 3	Stable Diffusion	Leonardo AI
Source	midjourney.com	openai.com	stability.ai	leonardo.ai
Parent Company	Midjourney	OpenAI	Stability AI	Leonardo AI
Platform	Discord	ChatGPT	WebUI	Leonardo AI
Technology	N/A; Proprietary Diffusion Model	OpenAI CLIP and GLIDE generation model	Stability AI Diffusion Model and OpenAI CLIP	Stability AI Diffusion Model and OpenAI CLIP
Data training	Microsoft COCO, Visual Genome, Flickr30k, others	N/A; public + licensed data sources	LAION-2B-en, LAION-5B with NSFW filter	SD dataset and possible additions
Data ethics	No consent from artists, use of copyrighted data	No consent from artists, use of copyrighted data	No consent from artists, use of copyrighted data	No consent from artists, use of copyrighted data
Ease of use	User-Friendly	User-Friendly	Challenging	User-Friendly
Speed of use	Moderate	Moderate	Fast	Moderate
Supported resolution	1024x1024 with aspect ratios (-ar)	1024x1024 or 1792x1024	Up to 2048x2048 with ratios	Up to 1536x1536 with ratios
Batch generation	No	No	Yes	Yes, limited to 8 images
Upscaling	Yes, to 2048x2048 or 4096x4096	No	Yes	Yes, once per image
Image editing	Limited	None	Extensive	Moderate
Models available	Limited	None	Unlimited	Moderate
Image rights	Conditional; full ownership with subscription	Full ownership	Stored locally; non-existent AI rights	Conditional; full ownership with subscription
Security	Low	Low	High	Low
Safe content	Yes	Yes	No restrictions	Yes
Price	Subscription	Subscription	Free, open source	Free tokens or subscription

Table 1: *Comparative Overview of Image Generation Platforms*

The comparison of platforms for image generation (Table 1) highlights that SD is particularly suitable for the game studio's need to design a workflow for specific use cases. The other platforms prioritise user-friendliness over personalisation. They typically offer fewer features and parameters, making it simpler to generate high-quality images quickly. Often, these platforms include built-in image enhancers that automatically improve the visual quality of images while reducing the possibility for users to edit

and control the output.

Regarding ethics, all text-to-image models referenced in Table 1 utilise copyrighted images in their training datasets, often without the original artists' consent. Midjourney CEO David Holz acknowledged that their dataset is essentially a comprehensive scrape of the internet, utilising openly available datasets for training, a common practice in the industry. Holz noted the challenge in sourcing a hundred million images with clear origins (Salkowitz, 2023). Further ethical considerations will be explored in Section 5.

It's important to note that while most SD models (SDv1.5, SDv2.0, SDXLv1.01¹) are free for commercial use, newer versions like SDXL Turbo are released under a non-commercial research license, restricting them to personal, non-commercial applications (Stability AI, 2023b). In the case of Dall-E, Microsoft covers potential future legal issues, but there remains ambiguity around the usage rights of the generated images. While they assure privacy, this legal grey area could potentially allow the use of generated data for model improvement, leading to uncertainties in the application of GenAI within organisational settings.

Choosing this platform is driven by the high level of security offered by running the model locally, ensuring full ownership of all inputs (e.g. prompts, custom models, etc.) and outputs (generated images), crucial for confidential game projects. SD provides immense customisation through its parameters and API access on the WebUI, allowing for extensive scripting possibilities. Furthermore, SD's flexibility in model selection, including downloading community models or training custom ones, is advantageous for tailoring to specific project needs. While SD has a lot of advantages, the complexity and breadth of its parameters result in a steep learning curve, requiring a solid understanding of the technical details to achieve the best outcomes, as well as high computing power to run the models locally.

1.5. Technical requirements and installation

Images from this thesis were generated using Stability AI's SD, employing the WebUI, an open-source project developed by AUTOMATIC1111 and other contributors (AUTOMATIC1111, 2023). Alternative solutions, such as subscription-based online services, were dismissed due to data security concerns. Another open-source option, ComfyUI (comfyanonymous, 2023), offers a modular approach with a node-based interface for creating SD pipelines and script customisation. However, the WebUI was preferred for its more straightforward, tab-based interface, offering greater ease of use for basic operations.

To install SD WebUI, the technical prerequisites include having a suitable GPU² with ample VRAM³ to handle the model's computational demands. The installation process involves installing required dependencies, then downloading the pre-trained models by cloning the repository locally. Users must also ensure they have enough storage and appropriate hardware specifications to run the AI models effectively (for the complete guide and updates, refer to the official WebUI GitHub page). To have the complete install, users should then add the extensions and models used for this thesis (refer to the Appendix).

To install and run the ArtistUI⁴ prototype, SD WebUI should be installed locally. In the local SD install folder, edit the .bat file and add --API in the command line to enable custom scripts and be able to run the ArtistUI. Then, the read-me instructions must be followed from the cloned ArtistUI repository.

¹SDXL is more recent, trained on higher resolution images but takes longer to generate images

²Graphic Processing Unit. A processor for rendering graphics.

³Video Random Access Memory. Memory used for storing image data for the GPU to display.

⁴As the GitHub repository is private, collaborators' invites are sent to the thesis's jury members.

2. Related Work

2.1. Algorithms in games

While GenAI is a recent innovation in content creation for video games, it is not the first of its kind. The gaming industry has seen significant impacts from the evolution of Procedural Content Generation (PCG) and traditional AI, altering the way games are developed, played, and experienced. This section explores these earlier technologies, examining how they have contributed to enhancing the efficiency and creativity in game development.

PCG uses algorithms to create game content automatically. Originating in early video games like *Rogue* (1980) to generate dungeons, PCG has evolved considerably. Generated content covers several categories, including basic elements like textures and sounds, environment, aspects like road networks and NPC behaviour, narrative constructs such as story and puzzles, overarching game design, and adaptable content (Hendrikx et al., 2013). Modern PCG applications range from creating diverse terrains to dynamic storylines, enhancing games' replayability and efficient data use. In *Minecraft*⁵, game worlds are completely generated procedurally, making them highly replayable as players always discover a new environment at the beginning of each of their games. Quest-based games can use algorithms to create a loot system based on the player's level.

Relying solely on PCG for the whole development of a game may be insufficient. While PCG's capabilities are extensive, allowing for the creation of virtually anything definable by rules, its application has grown more complex over time. In the 1980s, PCG's use was relatively straightforward, but modern tools like *Houdini*⁶ and the concept of open worlds have greatly complicated its rule sets. Sole dependence on PCG can result in games lacking in diversity, highlighting the importance of combining PCG with intentionally crafted content for variety and depth (Togelius et al., 2013). When the rules are too complex or undefined, ML becomes valuable, shifting the focus from rule definition to desired output, thereby enhancing the creative process in game development.

Moving beyond the scope of PCG, AI in games further enhances player interaction and game complexity. Game agents, powered by AI, take the evolution a step further by introducing sophisticated behaviours and decision-making abilities. AI allows Non-Playable Characters (NPC) to act with a degree of autonomy, learning from players' interactions to create more immersive and dynamic gaming experiences (Yildirim & Berg Stene, 2010). These AI-driven game agents contribute to the realism of the game world, offering players a richer and more engaging environment, adding to what PCG can provide to enhance game experiences.

The role of AI also extends to modern game development, as it can manage live game operations and long-term player engagement. AI now goes beyond creating game content to also acting as a producer, overseeing multiple games, player communities, and integrating real-world contexts (Yildirim & Berg Stene, 2010). This shift requires new research directions and data-driven approaches to AI applications in game production, enhancing player experience and addressing scalability challenges in game development. Researchers propose a vision where AI supports the entire game production pipeline, from creation to live operation, across multiple games and genres.

⁵A sandbox video game for building, exploring, and surviving in an open-world environment made up of blocks.

⁶A node-based software providing a procedural approach to create complex simulations, animations, and graphics.

2.2. Image generation

The current landscape of image generation is marked by models like DALL-E, IMAGEN or even Stable Diffusion. DALL-E, by OpenAI, leverages the Contrastive Language-Image Pre-Training (CLIP) network for high-fidelity image generation. Google's IMAGEN improves image-text alignment using advanced language models. SD, the open-source model from LMU Munich's CompVis group, improved text-to-image by enhancing the speed and image modification capabilities (Gozalo-Brizuela et al., 2023). These models made advancements in the field of creative image generation and are evolving fast. Yet, art is not the sole domain benefiting from generative image technologies. In the healthcare sector, transformers and diffusion models are used to enhance medical diagnosis. GenAI is used in various medical areas, including diffusion models for medical imaging (e.g. image reconstruction, image-to-image translation, image generation, and image classification), as well as transformers for diagnostic assistance, radiology interpretation or even clinical decision support (Shokrollahi et al., 2023). GenAI applications have enhanced clinical diagnosis accuracy and efficiency.

While SD excels in image generation, offering extensive parameters for image customisation, it faces a major challenge from its pretraining on a specific dataset, restricting its ability to produce images beyond its data scope. To address this issue, there are solutions to enhance image generation capabilities by customising the dataset used in addition to using the model checkpoint⁷. DreamBooth fine-tuning allows to customise the training model to specific datasets and tasks, improving its proficiency in generating specific types of images. Providing the model with a set of reference image of a specific subject, it learns to associate a specific word to it. Using Hypernetworks and DreamBooth models can diversify image inputs into SD with minimal training data allowing users to maintain the fidelity of the custom subject (Hidalgo et al., 2023). Text embedding, integrated into the WebUI, enables users to apply textual inversion, and unlike fine-tuning methods, it does not alter the model, allowing for the addition of custom keywords to add objects or styles. Researchers developed a user-friendly feature added to the WebUI to visually use text embedding (Rost & Andreasson, 2022). Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA) offers a great trade-off between file size and training power to generate images with custom styles. Textual inversions are smaller in size but not as powerful, and LoRAs are smaller and require less training time than the fine-tuning method. LORAs work by applying small changes to the cross-attention layers of the LDM (see Figure 1), and act as small model checkpoints modifiers (Andrew, 2023a).

⁷Models trained on SD base models to achieve a specific artistic direction (refer to Section 3.2.3)

Method	Model Size	Minimum Training Data	Use Cases	Description
DreamBooth Fine-tuning	Heavy 2–7 GBs	5–20 images	Artistic style, Subject	Fine-tunes the LDM itself until the new concept is understood
Textual Inversion	Light 100 KBs	3–5 images	Subject	Creates a special word embedding which captures the new concept
LoRA	Medium 2–200 MBs	15 images	Artistic style, Subject	Add new weights to the model by modifying SD model's cross-attention layers

Table 2: *Comparative Overview of SD model customisation*

Other solutions were developed to help users enhance the input, as well as better control the output using SD. A prompt optimiser uses supervised fine-tuning on a small set of manually engineered prompts, followed by reinforcement learning to discover better prompts (Hao et al., 2022). It aims to align user inputs with model-preferred prompts, improving the relevance and aesthetic quality of the generated images. In terms of better controlling the output, ControlNet was introduced in February 2023 and made a great advancement for image generation (Zhang et al., 2023). ControlNet is a neural network architecture designed to add spatial conditioning controls to the image generated. It is tested for various conditioning controls (e.g., edges, depth, segmentation, human pose), allowing the use of single or multiple conditions at once, with or without prompts.

Figure 2: ControlNet Architecture diagram. From "Stable Diffusion ControlNet Clearly Explained" by Steins, 2023.

The diagram (Figure 2) outlines the architecture for adding conditional control to text-to-image LDMs using ControlNet. It shows how an initial image goes through preprocessing to create a condition input (c_i), here using the linear model. This, alongside a textual prompt, influences the latent input (z_t) fed into the SD model, which iteratively generates an output image (z_{t-1}). ControlNet integrates with the SD process to apply final conditions (c_f) to refine the generated images. The results are images that accurately took as input the prompt in addition to the ControlNet image generated.

This section showed how GenAI is revolutionising image generation across various sectors, including art and healthcare. It particularly examined the enhancements in image generation using SD. While new tools are emerging rapidly, there remains a technical barrier to their use, with a notable gap in user-friendly applications. In video game development, there is a gap to fill for solutions that simplify text-to-image processes for artists, enabling easier integration into creative workflows.

2.3. GenAI in games

This section explores how GenAI in games not only enhances creative autonomy and complexity but also surpasses conventional AI by generating game content that is more varied, intricate, and contextually in-depth, despite being in its early stages.

GenAI has been integrated into game engines like Unity⁸, which is currently developing generative products. Unity Muse⁹ is an AI platform for generating 2D and 3D game assets, it can generate textures, sprites, and animated characters with a generative model trained on image data owned by Unity. It also features Muse Chat, an LLM powered by Azure AI and OpenAI technologies for troubleshooting. And Unity Sentis¹⁰, a tool that enables the importation of trained neural network models into the engine, expanding the range of AI applications to tackle complex challenges beyond the scope of traditional coding (Whitten, 2023).

Within the field of GenAI, LLMs are rapidly making their mark on the video game industry. A study presents a novel approach for life simulation games. They propose game agents capable of remembering experiences, synthesise memories into reflections for decision-making, and dynamically plan actions (Park et al., 2023). It allows for a complex simulation of social interactions within a game-like environment, where agents can form relationships, plan activities, and adapt to changes. The generative agents are integrated into an interactive sandbox 2D game inspired by *The Sims*¹¹, demonstrating individual and emergent social behaviours that are realistic and contextually appropriate. Their work opens new possibilities for the development of interactive, believable NPCs in gaming, contributing to more immersive and dynamic gaming experiences.

An examination of generative technologies over the last 5 years, aiming at defining the scope of GenAI, reveals that, in game development, PCG has received substantial attention, whereas image generation has been comparatively underexplored (García-Peñalvo & Vázquez-Ingelmo, 2023). This highlights the emerging nature of GenAI in the gaming domain and underscores the significant potential for expansion, a gap that this thesis seeks to address.

According to Bain & Company's report, GenAI's contribution to video game content could grow from less than 5% today to 50% in the next 5 to 10 years (Christofferson et al., 2023). GenAI has the potential for developing larger and more personalised games. Yet, they identify that the major obstacles to integrate these technologies will be system integration and data training to specific applications, artistic directions, and franchises. The authors suggest that game studios should proactively adapt their workflows and develop an AI-centred enterprise architecture strategy to seamlessly embrace GenAI's capabilities.

2.4. Creativity, efficiency, and innovation

The last sections highlighted the significant impact of PCG and AI in the video game industry, underscoring their roles in recent advancements. We have explored the cutting-edge developments in text-to-image generation, its evolving capabilities, and the untapped potential for game development, noting the current research gap in this field. The recent integration of GenAI in video games demonstrates its potential for further innovation. This section discusses how AI can also enhance creativity, efficiency, and innovation.

⁸A cross-platform game development engine that allows to create and deployment of interactive experiences.

⁹More information on <https://unity.com/products/muse>

¹⁰More information on <https://unity.com/fr/products/sentis>

¹¹A life simulation video game series that enables players to create and control virtual characters.

AI, particularly Large Language Models (LLMs) like ChatGPT, has been proven to significantly boost productivity and enhance the quality of creative tasks. GenAI can streamline task completion and augment idea-generation (Noy & Zhang, 2023). However, it's important to balance this view with caution, as while GenAI fosters creativity, it might also homogenise creative content, reducing diversity (Doshi & Hauser, 2023).

In game design, the principles of Explainable AI (XAI) (Zhu et al., 2018) advocate for a human-centred co-creation approach. This involves an in-depth understanding of AI systems by designers to foster effective collaboration. In addition, human-AI collaboration for creativity, the generation of novel and useful ideas or solutions (Amabile, 1996), once considered beyond AI's reach, is now achievable with GenAI (Fang He et al., 2023). This collaboration not only enhances efficiency but also amplifies the effectiveness of the design process.

3. Introduction to GenAI Techniques

This section aims to provide brief guidance on the prompting techniques and choice of parameters related to the WebUI features (AUTOMATIC1111, 2023) that are used in the workflow, Section 4. The generation information for each image in this section is detailed in the thesis's Appendix.

3.1. Prompting

The first technique needed to generate images is prompting. The workflow needs consistency. Therefore, users need to develop a generic, reusable process to build quality prompts. The following process is achieved through experimentation and testing. Prompts are a written way for users to communicate their idea to the AI, and to get controlled results, users need to describe the subject of the image, its context, the lighting, the colours, the artistic style, the perspective, the ambiance, etc. The anatomy of a quality prompt needs to be specific and use the right keywords. The method used for the workflow is to separate the prompts into different keywords categories (Table 3) and to approach prompt building as an iterative process, starting by choosing a style, a media, and a scene, then progressively adding more keywords to structure the generated image, adding one keyword at a time then generating the image to see the direct effect on the output. This iterative process must not be rushed.

Category	Keywords
Style	hyper-realistic, minimalist, surreal, abstract, steampunk, cyberpunk, mystical, moody, intricate details, hazy atmosphere, handcrafted, mysterious, ethereal, enigmatic, otherworldly
Camera	ultra close-up, fisheye lens, bird's-eye view, depth of field, low angle, full body length, 18mm shot, 35mm shot, 85mm shot, wide shot, panoramic, fixed focal length, macro, anamorphic, overhead, aerial, character sheet
Media	sketchbook, oil painting, photography, concept art, portrait, 3d rendering, octane render, cinematic still film, cinema scope, vector depiction, digital schematics, PBR material, watercolour, charcoal drawing, graffiti
Topic	(object) an old lighthouse, a futuristic city, a cyborg dragon (context, action) in a mystical forest, surrounded by exoplanets, crashing through the abyss
Extra tag	highly detailed, high budget, epic, masterpiece, 8k, photo real, inspirational, narrative-based visual, UHD image

Table 3: *Non-exhaustive list of keywords used for prompting.*

This section explains various aspects of prompt engineering and their impact on image generation, supported by illustrative examples. The discussion will cover the significance of prompt weights and how they influence the output. We will also explore the use of different styles as templates in prompts and negative prompts¹². Building on Table 3, each prompt category will be examined, the style, camera techniques, artistic media, topics, extra tags, then the impact of using prompting categories and their order, providing a comprehensive understanding of how these elements collectively shape the final generated image, and setting the methods used to build the evaluated workflow in Section 4.

3.1.1 Weights

The WebUI has specific syntax for prompting to adjust the weights of a keyword, using parenthesis or brackets can increase or decrease the weight of a keyword by a specific factor, the weight of a (*keyword*) in brackets is increased by a factor of *1.1* which is equivalent to writing (*keyword:1.1*). The opposite concept is used to decrease the emphasis of a keyword where (*keyword:0.25*) decreases its attention by a factor of $1/0.25 = 4$ (AUTOMATIC1111, 2023).

¹²Used to request the avoidance or exclusion of certain elements, ideas, or characteristics in the generated output.

Title	Category	Prompt	Image
Prompt	Style	mystical	
	Camera	depth of field	
	Media	studio photo	
	Topic	of a small creature, alien flora colourful landscape, detailed texture, soft fur	
	Extra Tag	breath-taking, professional art, highly detailed, 8k, unreal engine	
Added lexicon	Style	mystical	
	Camera	depth of field	
	Media	studio photo	
	Topic	of a small creature, alien flora colourful landscape, detailed texture, soft fur, exoskeleton, mechanical features	
	Extra Tag	breath-taking, professional art, highly detailed, 8k, unreal engine	
Weighted keywords	Style	mystical	
	Camera	depth of field	
	Media	studio photo	
	Topic	of a small (lizard:0.5)(cat:0.5) creature, alien flora colourful landscape, detailed texture, soft fur	
	Extra Tag	breath-taking, professional art, highly detailed, 8k, unreal engine	
	Style	mystical	
	Camera	depth of field	
	Media	studio photo	
	Topic	of a small (lizard:0.2)(cat:0.8) creature, alien flora colourful landscape, detailed texture, soft fur	
Extra Tag	breath-taking, professional art, highly detailed, 8k, unreal engine		

Figure 3: *Exploring Prompting Strategies: Sequential Order, Categorized Keywords, and Weighted Techniques in Image Generation*

Figure 3 images were generated with the same seed¹³, parameters, model checkpoint, and negative prompt to control the effect of only changing the positive prompt.

3.1.2 Preset styles

In addition to prompts, negative prompts (NP) are used to allow users to specify undesired elements to influence the generation of images. NPs are user-specific text as a form of conditioning to guide the model's output, leading to the generation of more controlled images by contrasting with the regular prompt. A good practice is to set a default NP for every image generated, this can be done in the

¹³The random number used to initialise the image generation. Using the same seed, prompts, and parameters results in the same generated image.

WebUI by creating a `styles.csv` file in the `stable-diffusion-WebUI` folder¹⁴. Prompt styles act as a template for positive and NPs.

Image			
Prompt	a mad scientist with crazy goggles	a samurai girl, pink hair, gun	a man wearing a onesie, gun
Styles	Fortnite + Fortnite negative	Fortnite + Fortnite negative	Fortnite + Fortnite negative

Figure 4: *Employing Preset Styles as Prompting Templates*

The generated images (Figure 4) use the following styles: Fortnite, Fortnite Negative (see below) and Default Negative (see Appendix I). The character pose is from the ControlNet open pose model, the three images have the same parameters.

- Fortnite: saturated (solid colour background:1.5), [prompt], cartoony game character with exaggerated proportions, extravagant outfit, minimalist modelling, (low poly:0.5), (octane render:1.2)
- Fortnite Negative: realistic shading, realistic shadow, (shading:1.3), (shadow:1.2), (detailed:1.2), (realism:1.2)

3.1.3 Style, media, and topic

The Style category determines the visual and aesthetic character of an image, such as being realistic or surreal, and can be defined by one or several keywords for more precision. The Media category indicates the methods and materials used in creating the artwork. Topic, meanwhile, covers the subject matter or theme depicted. For ethical reasons, we avoid directly naming artists to describe styles. Instead, we describe the style itself using relevant terms. For instance, for Ukiyo-e, a prominent style from Japan's Edo Period, we use ChatGPT to obtain a related lexicon and apply the lexicon appropriately in the prompt categories (see Figure 5).

¹⁴Refer to Appendix I for the content of the `styles.csv` file

Category	Prompt	Image
Style	Ukiyo-e style, Edo Period, dark, gritty	
Camera	Full body length	
Media	Sumi-e, Japanese Woodblock painting, flat coloration, outline emphasis, stylised elements, asymmetrical composition, Japanese calligraphic Seals	
Topic	Demon Assassin's Creed character, Japanese character, hood, Japanese text description, golden cape, Wisteria, mountains in the background	
Extra Tag	Breath-taking, sharp drawing, professional art, wallpaper, highly detailed, 8k	

Figure 5: Exploring the Impact of Lexical Choices on Style, Media, and Topic in Image Prompting

3.1.4 Camera

The Camera category encompasses photographic techniques and perspectives, such as close-up, fisheye lens, bird's-eye view, and depth of field. It also includes specific framing styles like full body length, wide shots, and different focal lengths. Other elements in this category include macro photography, anamorphic perspective, and aerial views, all contributing to the unique visual narrative of the image.

	Ultra close-up	Fisheye Lens	Bird's-eye view	Depth of field	Low angled	Full body length	18mm shot	35mm shot	85mm shot
cyberrealistic v3.3									
dreamshaper v8									
juggernautXL v7									
rundiffusionXL beta									

Figure 6: Assessing the Impact of the 'Camera' Prompting Category on Different Model Checkpoints in Image Generation

Figure 6 shows the camera techniques on the x-axis, and four different model checkpoints on the y-axis. To test the effect of using the different keywords from the camera category (Table 3) for prompting, the images all have the same seed.

The prompt is as follows: *Hyper-realistic [camera technique] photography, an austere old man standing*

on the street, highly detailed, 8k, masterpiece.

The chosen subject, a portrait, is a good fit to test the different camera techniques as keywords such as “full-body length” would not fit every subject. The differences can be subtle, but for the 3 last columns (18, 35 and 85mm shot), there is a noticeable variation in the “distortion” of the faces, accompanied by observable shifts in the perspective lines of the street, mirroring the nuances found in real-life photography. The first two rows of images are generated with models trained on SD v1.5 (in a 768x768 pixels resolution), and the last two rows were generated with models trained on SDXL v1.0 (in a 1024x1024 pixels resolution) to test if the keywords list for the camera prompting category would work on the most common model checkpoints.

3.1.5 Extra tag

The Extra Tag category is not related to the subject of the image; it is composed of keywords to improve the quality of the generated image. Researchers developed a framework for prompt engineering, enhancing the quality and relevance of images generated from text-to-image models (Hao et al., 2022). Their study shows an innovative approach to align user inputs with model-preferred prompts, demonstrating that keywords such as those in the Extra Tag category of this thesis lead to more aesthetically pleasing image outcomes.

User Input	Optimized Prompt
A rabbit is wearing a space suit	A rabbit is wearing a space suit, digital Art, Trending cinematographic artstation
Several railroad tracks with one train passing by	several railroad tracks with one train passing by, hyperdetailed, artstation, cgsociety, 8 k
The roof is wet from the rain	the roof is wet from the rain, intricate, elegant, highly detailed, digital painting, artstation, concept art, smooth, sharp focus, illustration,
Cats dancing in a space club	Cats dancing in a space club, digital painting, artstation, concept art, soft light, hdri, smooth, sharp focus, illustration, fantasy,

Figure 7: Comparative display of image generation: Stable Diffusion outputs from user inputs vs. optimised prompts, showcasing enhanced aesthetic quality. From “Optimising Prompts for Text-to-Image Generation” by Hao et al., 2022.

3.1.6 Prompting categories and sequential order

Title	Prompt	Image		
Categorized and Arranged in Categories	Minimalist, intricate details, close-up shot, octane render, 3D rendering, heavy pistol, decorated with hand-painted drawing of an orange koi fish, photoreal, 4k, masterpiece			
Unsystematic Arrangement without Categories	Photoreal, decorated with hand-painted drawing of an orange koi fish, 3D rendering, masterpiece, intricate details, heavy pistol, minimalist, 4k, octane render, close-up shot			

Figure 8: *Impact of Categorisation and Sequential Order on Image Accuracy*

The generated images (Figure 8) demonstrate the impact of arranging keywords into categories. For this purpose, the chosen prompt is a difficult task for most models without a well-structured prompt, as it has a combination of two subjects: a koi fish and a gun that are not often used together (models tend to dissociate the fish object from the gun object).

AI models, especially in generative processes, rely on machine learning techniques. The generated output tends to represent the “most probable” result based on the model’s learned patterns from the training data. Therefore, it is easier to generate familiar subjects where there is ample training data available. In addition, SD models may struggle with intricate subjects, such as the placement of elements in the image. A common limitation is the image composition, which can be addressed using regional prompting, an extension that allows users to specify prompts for specific regions of an image (refer to Appendix VI).

Figure 9: Impact of Categorisation and Sequential Order on Image Accuracy

In most cases, the order of the five categories (Figure 3) helps users to generate images that conform to the prompt. However, due to the black box nature of the AI models used, it is difficult to confirm that this order is the most efficient way of prompting. The images generated (Figure 9) are all the order combinations possible for prompting with the regrouped keywords in the five categories¹⁵. The images framed in green are those that accurately adhere to the prompt, based on criteria such as having a functional gun with a koi fish painted on it. Each image includes the five letters representing distinct prompting categories and their sequence (e.g., SMCTE denoting Subject, Media, Camera, Topic, and Extra tag). The table’s rows correspond to the images that start with each category. The results from Figures 3 and 9 demonstrate a correlation between categorising keywords and achieving more accurate generated images. However, it does not establish the most effective sequential order for accurate output. Nevertheless, in Section 4, we will adopt the following order-SMCTE-in our workflow to maintain consistency in our prompting method. These results were produced with the dynamic prompt extension (Appendix VI).

3.2. Parameters walk-through

This section dives into key parameters for text-to-image generation, clarifying the role of model checkpoints. It establishes best practices for use in Section 4, starting with steps and samplers and their influence on the LDM’s denoising process. Following this, it discusses the available SD models, their applications, and the use of model checkpoints.

3.2.1 Steps

The most important parameters in image generation are the *model*, the *sampler*, and the *steps*, as they have a crucial role in the diffusion process. This process is parameterised by noise levels; as the

¹⁵Figure 9 is an enlarged view of the complete figure containing all the generated images. The comprehensive figure is available in Appendix V.

steps increase, the noise decreases, and the image gets more defined. Samplers are responsible for the denoising process of the image. This process is iterated on a specified number of steps, and a sample image is generated at each step. The sampler algorithm defines how the image is denoised, and the noise scheduler defines how much the image gets denoised. Noise reduction is not linear, the noise scheduler removes a large amount of noise during the first steps for faster progress, then removes less and less noise to define the details of the image.

Figure 10: *Sampling Steps of the Denoising Process*

Figure 10 shows the images generated at each iteration of the sampling steps for 10 steps. The steps of the sampling process can be saved using a custom script (AUTOMATIC1111, 2023). The image prompt is “a pirate” with the added styles *Craft Clay* and *Default Negative*.

3.2.2 Samplers

In image generation, the chosen sampler significantly affects the speed at which the final image converges. The sampler’s role is to execute the denoising process, transforming a completely random latent space image into a clear image. This is achieved by systematically estimating and removing predicted noise, following a specific noise schedule.

Section 4 of the research will examine two key approaches in image generation using SD. Initially, for quick image generation, we employ either the *Euler A* or *UniPC* sampler, prioritising speed over intricate details. Conversely, for the final image generation where quality is crucial, we use the *DPM++ SDE Karras* sampler. This choice is due to its ability to greatly improve the image’s clarity and overall aesthetic.

The *Euler A* sampler, being stochastic, introduces noise at each step and leads to non-convergent images. On the other hand, the *DPM++ SDE Karras* sampler uses Karras’ noise schedule, enhancing image quality in the later stages of generation, providing a higher level of detail (Andrew, 2023b).

3.2.3 Models and model checkpoints

It’s key to understand the difference between models and model checkpoints in the context of Stable Diffusion (SD). The *SDXL v1.0* model is an advanced version of the *SD v1.5* model, featuring enhanced image generation capabilities. This upgrade involves combining a large base model of 6.6 billion parameters with a refiner model, which together improve image quality and prompt interpretation. However, its size demands more computational power and makes it not as quick as smaller models like *SD v1.5* in generating images (Andrew, 2023c).

On the other hand, *model checkpoints* are pre-trained SD weights. They are trained based on a specific SD model version (e.g., SDXL v1.0, SD v1.5) for generating images with a specific artistic direction (e.g., specialised in realistic, anime, RPG, etc.) (Andrew, 2022).

Figure 11: *Experimenting with Different Artistic Directions via Prompting and Model Checkpoints*

Figure 11 displays three game characters set in a futuristic, sci-fi world with orange tones and distant exoplanets. The first image, photorealistic in style, is created using a realistic model checkpoint through text-to-image generation. The subsequent two images, derived from the first, are produced using image-to-image generation, applying cartoon and anime model checkpoints, respectively. This comparison aims to explore the influence of pre-trained weights in model checkpoints and assess their effectiveness in achieving varied artistic styles from a single reference image.

Section 4 will focus on generating images with a realistic, SD v1.5 based, model checkpoint for faster image generation and for its higher compatibility with the extensions needed during the workflow, such as ControlNet.

4. ADR Methodology

Our research is conducted by a small team in a leading game studio, working on a pre-production phase project. Our team includes, among others, a concept artist, a technical artist, and a technical director. We are focused on GenAI for image generation, with the manager supervising and providing feedback. The studio tasks us with testing and developing GenAI solutions. Our work primarily centres on text-to-image generation but also extends to generative 3D and video content. As a technical artist, I handle

the research and development of the text-to-image solutions, the technical director reviews and guides my work, and the concept artist tests our GenAI solutions, offering practical feedback (refer to Table 4 for team roles).

Member	ADR Role	Description
Yonah Bole (Technical Artist)	Researcher	Researchers utilise theoretical and technological expertise to design and implement solutions, test them for feedback, and adjust based on the ADR method. They lead the research process, collect and analyse data, and contribute to theoretical foundations for informed solution development.
Frédéric Saclier (Technical Director)	Practitioner	Practitioners offer practical hypotheses and knowledge of organisational practices, actively participating in solution design and implementation. Their role is vital for ensuring solutions align with real-world constraints and are feasible in practice.
Carla Ragache (Concept Artist)	End-User	End-users contribute valuable insights into their needs, preferences, and experiences during the co-creation process. Actively involved in providing feedback on prototypes, they help refine solutions to meet the actual needs of beneficiaries.

Table 4: *ADR roles of the GenAI team members.*

Following Sein et al. (2011) methodology, we proceed with the following steps: (1) problem formulation; (2) building, intervention, and evaluation (BIE); (3) reflection and learning; (4) formalisation of learning. The problem formulation identifies the need and the organisational context as well as the challenges of incorporating a novel technology. The design phase is the design of the workflow with the iterative process in the targeted environment. It encompasses building the artifact, the feedback from the organisation, and the evaluation. The reflection and learning stage focuses on applying the feedback to the artifact, applying the learnings from the design phase. Then the formalisation of learning covers the insights from the conducted studies. Figure 12 illustrates the research design. The ADR stages, principles, and data collection are provided in Table 5.

Figure 12: *Research Design*

ADR Stage	ADR Principle	Justification	Activities	Data collection	Artifact
Problem formulation	P1: Practice-inspired research	The study is driven by the lack of accessible GenAI for game development. The problem formulation comes from practitioners, end-users, the researcher, existing technologies, and the literature review.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. understanding the need of the organisation 2. reviewing the literature on GenAI in games 3. formulating the research questions 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. meetings with practitioners and end-users 2. weekly GenAI meetings 3. studio workshops on AI 4. literature review 	Recognition: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. gathering information for relevant use cases 2. Identifying the factors driving GenAI adoptions in the video game industry
BIE	P3: Reciprocal shaping	The workflow is influenced by two domains, the technological and the organisational context	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. designing multiple use case workflows 2. choosing to focus on the character sheet workflow 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. using Qualtrics survey data and interviews to gather feedback on the alpha version 2. evaluating the beta version with a semi-structured interview 	Alpha version: Designing a workflow to guide users for generating images with the SD WebUI. Beta version: Designing a simplified UI (ArtistUI) with automated choice of parameters
	P4: Mutually influential roles	Researcher and practitioners worked together and shared their knowledge	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. user-testing the workflow, evaluating if it was user-friendly for non-technical users 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. weekly GenAI meetings 	
	P5: Authentic and concurrent evaluation	Natural controls were done by receiving constant feedback by practitioners			
Reflection and learning	P6: Guided emergence	The former design was constantly reshaped by the organisational context as the end-users and the practitioners tested and gave feedback on the artifact	Recognising the challenges faced by the non-technical end-users and the integration of GenAI in the game industry	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. meetings with technical director, concept artists, and programmers 2. weekly GenAI meetings 3. studio workshops on AI 	Emerging version and realisation: The revised version of the workflow, the challenges in each phase emerging from organisational and technological context, and a reflection on how these challenges were addressed through the UI design
Formalisation of learnings	P7: Generalised outcomes	Generalisation is hard to reach with such a novel technology, but the resulting ensemble serve as a base for future advancements in the use of GenAI	Gathering views from different studio within the company and different experts	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. meetings with technical director, concept artists, and programmers 2. weekly GenAI meetings 3. studio workshops on AI 	Ensemble version: Ensemble embodying a simplified UI to hide to complexity of GenAI technologies, with a specific use case that can be modified and applied to the next use cases and GenAI technologies

Table 5: ADR stages, principles, justifications, activities, and data collection for each stage

4.1. Problem formulation

In this research, the IS artifact of the ADR methodology is the GenAI workflow for text-to-image generation. The organisational context is a game studio that aims to integrate GenAI in its development pipeline, and the problem setting here is how to integrate and use text-to-image technologies using Stable Diffusion. The main challenge here is the unfriendly UI of the WebUI, its steep learning curve, and technical complexities (see Figure 13).

The goal is for concept artists, whose job is to create the visual designs of a game during the pre-production process with a specific artistic direction, to be able to use GenAI and integrate it into their workflow without having to be extremely technical about this technology. The chosen use case is to generate the concept art of a character by generating a character sheet with 4 different views of a game character in one image. We aim to design a workflow while allowing for its emergence in the organisational context, to evaluate its usefulness and to iterate with the feedback received.

Figure 13: *Stable Diffusion WebUI by Automatic1111.*

In the problem formulation phase, an extensive literature review was conducted, which delved into four pivotal areas: the use of Procedural Content Generation (PCG) and AI in gaming, which provided insights into the foundational implementation of AI in this domain; the current state of text-to-image generation technologies to gauge their efficiency and capability; the application of GenAI in gaming, with a focus on the prevalent use of LLMs and the nascent stage of text-to-image technologies; and the concepts of creativity, efficiency, and innovation about AI and GenAI, exploring the potential for AI to engage in creative processes beyond the basic functions seen in conventional game AI.

In this ADR phase, we engaged in various meetings and discussions with professionals from a broad spectrum of roles within the industry. These interactions were crucial to comprehend the challenges of

integrating GenAI and the specific nuances of the organisational context. At this point, there was a general scepticism about the feasibility of implementing text-to-image technologies into game production pipelines.

Simultaneously, to deepen technical understanding, we participated in AI workshops and weekly GenAI discussions, while continuously monitoring new research papers and open-source models for experimentation. For instance, the release of ControlNet marked a significant step forward, as it provided enhanced control over image outputs, greatly influencing the design of our workflow.

Evaluating the quality of the generated image is challenging. The metrics we considered were:

- Image relevance and accuracy: the degree to which the image matches the input prompt, and its consistency in producing accurate outputs.
- Visual quality: absence of artifacts and “hallucinations” (objects irrelevant to the image context).
- Creativity and originality: whether the image serves as a qualitative source of ideas for artists.

The artifact consists of three key components. First, a structured concept art generation workflow (see Figure 15) was developed to guide artists in using the open-source Automatic1111 WebUI. This workflow helps them navigate prompting, parameter tuning, and the overall complexity of the standard SD interface. Second, the WebUI itself, serves as the user interface through which artists input their creative intent. Initially, this interface required following the external workflow for effective use. Third, the SD model functions as the back-end engine that processes the parameters and generates images based on the artist’s input (see Figure 14).

Figure 14 illustrates this initial setup: artists interact with the Automatic1111 WebUI to create images, guided by the designed workflow, while the SD model runs in the background. To improve this process, ArtistUI was later developed as a simplified, artist-friendly interface. It abstracts away the technical complexity by embedding key configurations, such as a system prompt and model parameters, removing the need for users to rely on the external workflow.

Figure 14: High-level overview of the artefact

4.2. BIE

This ADR phase covers the building, intervention, and evaluation of the designed artifact. The alpha version of the ADR is the workflow (see Figure 15). This version of the artifact is a flowchart, intended to be used as a guide in addition to the SD WebUI.

Before focusing on the character sheet workflow, many use cases were tested, such as a props workflow where the need from the artist is to quickly generate texture variations for a game prop¹⁶. Many prompting techniques were tested, and we iterated between different ways of prompting. We decided to follow the prompt categories and a specific sequential order that were tested and validated. In addition, parameters were tested and iterated over; results showed that an efficient way to generate images was to first use parameters for a fast generation process, then enhance and upscale the image in a slower process with higher resolution output (refer to Section 3 for tests and results).

The character creation process outlined in the designed workflow involves four key steps:

1. An initial image generation step uses a reference image to create four character views. Users formulate a prompt based on a template, then generate four images and select one.
2. The chosen image is processed through upscaling and texture variation, generating fewer images with high-resolution parameters.
3. The preferred image is uploaded into Photoshop to sketch and realistically generate parts of the character, such as weapons or clothing, using the inpainting feature.
4. The final phase involves upscaling the image with a specialised extension that enhances facial details, increasing the resolution from 1024×476 (step 1) to 2054×940 (step 4).

¹⁶Any in-game object or item, whether functional or decorative, e.g., a helmet.

Figure 15: Visual Representation of Character Workflow for Concept Art Generation on A1111 WebUI, the ADR alpha version.

Following tests of the character workflow with end-users varying in their familiarity with GenAI, it became clear that using the SD WebUI in its original form was too complex, even when guided by the workflow.

Consequently, we shifted focus to develop a more user-friendly iteration: the ArtistUI prototype, the ADR beta version. Designed to simplify the process, this version automates much of the workflow. Users are only required to input their prompt, with most parameters being pre-configured for each step. As the ArtistUI evolved, even the prompt process was streamlined, users only needed to input the subject, and the system combined it with predefined prompting categories, default prompts, and extra tags, enhancing the generated image quality.

Each update of the ArtistUI incorporated additional features or automation enhancements:

- **Version 1.0** allowed users to choose the style, camera, media, and negative prompt.
- **Version 1.1** simplified the UI by hiding debug information irrelevant to users.
- **Version 1.2** integrated ControlNet, allowing for advanced image control using depth or lineart

conditions.

- **Version 1.3**, used in the final evaluation phase, implemented all four steps of the character workflow directly into the UI with pre-configured parameters. It maintained the objective of enabling qualitative output while minimising user input complexity.

Figure 16: *The ArtistUI*. (a) *Version 1.0*, (b) *Version 1.1*, (c) *Version 1.2*, (d) *Version 1.3*

Version 1.3 (see figure 16) is the version used for the user testing during the semi-structured interview (refer to the Appendix). Previous versions allowed to get a better understanding of the SD WebUI API and how to code the payload for each feature, so that in this version, the character workflow could be implemented. The goal remains the same, having a simplified UI with the least user inputs while having the same qualitative results as the generated images from the workflow (the ADR alpha version). It was designed to have the same 4 steps as the workflow, but the parameters are pre-configured.

4.3. Reflection and learnings

Six studio members with varying backgrounds and GenAI familiarity were selected to test both the alpha and the beta versions. End-users were asked to participate in a survey. Their task was to experiment

with the alpha version, following the workflow to guide them through the character workflow. They were asked to provide their background details (role, experience, AI familiarity, and SD usage) and submit feedback on the workflow’s usability. The beta version (ArtistUI) was evaluated with a semi-structured interview (Appendix IV), focusing on the following topics: integration, efficiency, creativity, innovation, UI experience, comparative analysis, practicality, accessibility, and future perspectives. Then we collected a sample of participant-generated images from the alpha and the beta versions. Figure 17 displays three of the four workflow steps (S) and the images generated by the participants (P).

Version	Steps	Participants results		
Workflow using SD Web UI	S1 1st image generation (txt2img)			
	S3 Photoshop Sketch			
	S4 Final Image			
ArtistUI	S1 1st image generation (txt2img)			
	S3 Photoshop Sketch			
	S4 Final Image			

Figure 17: User-generated images using the workflow (top row) and the ArtistUI (bottom row). S1–S3 denote the workflow steps; P1–P3 refer to participant outputs.

While all participants successfully generated quality results, the survey revealed a predominantly negative experience with the SD WebUI workflow. Users reported that the parameters were unclear, the interface was not intuitive, and the workflow was difficult to follow. One participant explicitly suggested that the solution should offer fewer parameters and a single input field for prompts to ease the process. The survey results are summarised in Figure 18. While responses were generally positive regarding clarity and usefulness, they also highlighted significant confusion due to the WebUI’s complex parameters and required technical knowledge.

Figure 18: *Participants’ opinion on the WebUI. Five-point Likert scale from strongly disagree to strongly agree*

Conversely, the semi-structured interviews indicated a more positive response towards the ArtistUI. Participants unanimously agreed on its increased efficiency and ease of use for generating character sheets, highlighting the advantages of a simplified UI, such as a more efficient generation process, describing it as faster, easier, and more straightforward to follow than the alpha version. Users also affirmed that this tool was useful in diminishing the mental workload necessary to use technical GenAI tools such as SD WebUI and affirmed that the tool helps with ideation and enhancing the creative process (refer to Appendix IV).

4.4. Formalisation of learnings

This section covers the insights derived from the conducted studies involving the six studio members. The feedback from the alpha version, obtained through a survey that guided participants through the character workflow, highlighted the challenges faced with the SD WebUI workflow. This feedback was primarily negative, as the participants found the workflow difficult to understand and less user-friendly, which impacted their overall experience negatively.

Contrastingly, the beta version testing, which involved the use of the ArtistUI, revealed a significant shift in user experience. The semi-structured interviews conducted post-testing provided valuable insights into the effectiveness of the ArtistUI. Participants unanimously reported an enhanced user experience, noting the simplified UI’s increased efficiency and ease of use in generating character sheets. This positive shift is clearly reflected in the answers provided, where participants acknowledged the simplicity and streamlined process brought about by the ArtistUI. They highlighted how the tool facilitated the generation of the character sheet, aiding in the decision-making process for production use. Additionally,

the tool was commended for aiding in ideation and overcoming creative blocks, thus underscoring its potential in enhancing creativity and innovation in the game development process.

The formalisation of knowledge is completed by insights gained throughout all ADR phases. Creating the artifact based on ADR principles enabled the development of a solution guided by both theoretical and organisational context, with continuous iterations and evaluation. These solutions aided in integrating GenAI into the artist's design process, demonstrating its potential to enhance creativity and efficiency in art creation, and addressing challenges in GenAI integration into the gaming industry.

5. Discussion

In this section, we discuss the thesis's findings, beginning with an evaluation of the ADR outcomes. We then examine the research's technical, human, and ethical limitations. The section concludes by offering alternative solutions and suggestions for future research directions.

5.1. Comments on the findings

The ADR phases led to the development of solutions guided by theoretical and organisational considerations, incorporating GenAI into the artist's design process, showcasing its creative and efficient capabilities, and addressing integration challenges in the gaming industry. This research underscores the need for more than just workflows; user-friendly tools are essential for easier adoption and practical use. The research enriches our understanding of integrating GenAI in game development, showing its role in enhancing creativity and efficiency in creative sectors, emphasising the need for tools that are accessible and effective for managerial implementation in an organisational context.

Yet, the ADR research can benefit from improvements. Increasing the sample size and diversity beyond one game studio for broader cultural representation would enhance the generalisability of the results (ADR Principle 7). The ADR's focus was narrowed due to the six-month time constraint, leading to a lack of emphasis on Principle 2 (the ingrained artifact theory). Additionally, expanding the research to include various contexts and applications beyond 2D character sheets would offer a more comprehensive understanding of the technology's potential.

The semi-structured interview included some negative feedback as P5 expressed scepticism about GenAI's ability to accelerate the creative process for artists. They noted that the overly simplified UI lacked sufficient control over the output, highlighting a trade-off that needs consideration during artifact development.

5.2. Limitations

This research, while presenting a comprehensive exploration and development, recognises various limitations affecting the applicability, ethical considerations, and ecological implications of the proposed GenAI solutions. Technical challenges, human-centric concerns, ethical dilemmas, and ecological repercussions are discussed, with a brief overview of alternative solutions and methodological advancements aiming to address these constraints for a more responsible integration of AI in the gaming industry.

5.2.1 Technical

This research faces technical limitations affecting reproducibility and generalisation. Installing SD, along with necessary model checkpoints and extensions, is complex. The computational requirements for testing the workflow are substantial; it necessitates a high-performance PC equipped with a robust

graphics card and ample local memory. Additionally, the rapid evolution of technology (e.g., from SD to SDXL, new extensions, etc.) may soon render aspects of this thesis obsolete, though it can still serve as a foundational reference for future technologies.

5.2.2 Human

Addressing human limitations in this context is crucial. Algorithm aversion, characterised by scepticism towards automated decisions (Burton et al., 2019), was evident both in the semi-structured interview responses and within the organisational context concerning GenAI. Despite some hesitation about GenAI in the gaming industry, it is important to note that existing PCG in gaming still heavily relies on human input for issues like unrealistic terrain. Adapting to GenAI might not result in immediate drastic changes, indicating that a gradual adoption strategy could be more beneficial as the technology progresses.

Moreover, there's a noticeable divide in users' understanding and comfort with AI technologies. While the ADR's evaluation shows GenAI tools are seen as beneficial for creativity, Doshi and Hauser (2023) raise concerns about AI potentially diminishing the diversity of new content, leading to more uniform creative outcomes. A limitation that was noted by P5 when they stated that generated images often had too many details, contrast, and saturation.

5.2.3 Ethical

For the ethical limitations, we discuss various concerns. Initially highlighted in Section 1, these models require extensive data for training. The use of images without copyright permissions, as in early versions of SD, raises legal and ethical concerns, particularly when commercialising generated images in video games. While extensive training data increases models' performance, it is necessary to consider the trade-off between performance and ethics. As technology advances, maintaining ethical and secure practices with smaller data sets becomes increasingly important.

Generative models often magnify biases from their training data, with reports of SD reinforcing harmful stereotypes about race and gender (Nicoletti & Bass, 2023). Additionally, issues like deepfakes and not-safe-for-work (NSFW) content in models like SD need addressing. A concern that we took into account in the ADR solution, which implemented the default negative prompt to ensure content safety (Appendix I).

Legally, the rapid pace of technological advancement outstrips policy development, creating ambiguity around copyright infringement, especially concerning AI-generated art. Copyrighting AI output may depend on the level of human involvement in the generated content produced (Vincent, 2022), but we need clear legal directives to be certain.

Ecologically, following ever-advancing technologies poses moral questions. The environmental impact was assessed with a significant carbon footprint. The training for SD v1, considering hardware, runtime, cloud provider and compute region, was used to calculate the environmental impact, and the estimated carbon emitted is 11.250 tonnes of CO₂ (CompVis, 2022). Equivalent to 6.6 Paris-NY round trips. In addition to this number, implementing the ADR solution in game studios, with continuous cloud storage for storing and accessing large images, will further exacerbate ecological concerns.

Finally, GenAI's impact on the workforce cannot be overlooked. The potential replacement of human artists raises ethical issues. GenAI's influence on the labour market and its implications for creative jobs are critical considerations (Walkowiak & MacDonald, 2023).

5.3. Alternative solutions

Firstly, addressing methodological limitations, future studies should engage in a comprehensive ADR process, adhering strictly to all ADR principles. This approach should include a larger sample size and incorporate participants from various game studios to introduce cultural diversity for more robust statistical results and to enhance the generalisability of the research outcomes. Moreover, in Section 3 when testing and exploring optimal parameters for image generation, it is advisable to go beyond the metrics mentioned by also integrating human evaluations for a more objective assessment of image quality. Additionally, simplifying the installation process is beneficial for ensuring the reproducibility of the research. A feasible solution could be to offer a single downloadable zip file containing all necessary model checkpoints, samplers, extensions, etc.

Secondly, from an ethical and technological perspective, tackling algorithm aversion and promoting ethical usage is important. Alternative solutions could incorporate AI models based on the principle of explainable AI (XAI), which emphasises the transparency and interpretability of AI decisions, enabling users to understand and trust AI outputs (Zhu et al., 2018). We could explore different AI models or training methods to address current limitations, including the development of custom-trained models tailored to specific game franchises based on ethical and controlled training data. Additionally, future solutions should improve the ArtistUI. For instance, instead of manually writing styles in prompts, users could select styles through clickable images, seamlessly integrating their choices into the prompt, and the ArtistUI features could expand to more than the character sheet workflow.

6. Conclusion

This research explored the integration of GenAI, particularly through Stable Diffusion models, into the game development process. The findings show that GenAI can significantly enhance both the efficiency and creativity of artists. By designing user-friendly workflows and interfaces, the study demonstrates how GenAI can become more accessible, bridging the gap between complex technologies and practical artistic use. It also outlines strategies for overcoming integration challenges in studio environments.

From a practitioner's perspective in the creative industry, AI seems best positioned as a supportive tool, not a replacement for human creativity. Discussions with practitioners highlight the most valuable use cases in automating repetitive or technical tasks, such as mesh cleanup or retopology¹⁷ in 3D software like Blender¹⁸. As shown in this thesis, GenAI can also support ideation by generating quick visual variations to accelerate feedback loops with art directors. However, core creative decisions should remain human-led. We recommend AI be guided by technically skilled artists, as this human-AI collaboration produces higher quality results and preserves artistic intent.

Looking ahead, this research opens avenues for extending GenAI applications, such as integrating SD into Blender for texture projection and repetitive task automation. Beyond gaming, the user-centred methods developed here offer a model for applying GenAI in fields like animation, advertising, and fashion. By focusing on usability, feedback, and domain-specific workflows, this approach helps ensure that AI augments rather than replaces creativity. Overall, the thesis lays a foundation for integrating AI in ways that empower artists and support innovation across the creative industries.

¹⁷Process where the mesh (the structure of vertices, edges, and faces) of a 3D model is redesigned or optimized

¹⁸A 3D computer graphics software for creating animations, visual effects, 3D objects, and more.

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Appendices

Appendix I – Prompting Styles Template

The `styles.csv` file used should be located at `./stable-diffusion-webui/styles.csv` and contains the following styles:

Negative prompts:

- Default Negative: low-quality, watermark, deformed, distorted anatomy, poor artistry, NSFW, cleavage, nudity, naked, explicit content, mutated features, extra limbs, extra fingers, ugly, missing body parts, disconnected elements, malformed, abnormal proportions, aberrant hands, aberrant feet, aberrant legs, aberrant fingers
- Fortnite Negative: realistic shading, realistic shadow, (shading:1.3), (shadow:1.2), (detailed:1.2), (realism:1.2)

Positive prompts:

- 3D Rendering: (octane render:1.2), volumetric light, centred in neutral background, digital rendering, digital art, 3D render, smooth curves, blender art, 3D object rendering, volumetric, unreal engine
- Cinematic: in a cinematic scene, cinematic lighting, filmic composition, sharp focus, dramatic lighting, dramatic colours, hyper-detailed scenes, lifelike textures, depth and perspective, atmospheric effects, cinematic visuals
- Portrait: skin details, realistic facial features, detailed (face pores:1.5) and skin, character portrait, emotional expression, (facial fuzz:1.3), professional photography, lifelike eyes, realistic skin tones, detailed portraiture, (wrinkles:0.35), (imperfect skin:1.1), facial beauty mark
- Digital Drawing: (brushstroke:1.2), digital brush texture, digital canvas, digital illustration, illustrative artwork, trending on artstation, (brushwork:1.2)
- Sketchbook: realistic sketch, rough sketch, mix of bold dark lines and loose lines, bold lines, on paper, sharp drawing, professional art, hand-drawn lines, sketching realism, detailed sketchwork
- Manga: anime studio artwork, anime characters, manga style inking, shonen manga, Japanese art, inked, detailed background, expressive characters
- Indie Game: set in an indie game environment, artistic design, indie artistry, handcrafted, original concept, indie game aesthetics, narrative-driven, masterpiece artwork, stylised, artistic, hand drawn, moody lighting
- Craft Clay: sculpted clay art, handcrafted clay, clay modelling, clay texture, clay figurines,

-
- clay craftwork, artistic clay forms, textured surfaces, craft clay details, sculpture
 - Isometric: (set in a voxel isometric world:1.2), isometric style, 3D grid, isometric render,
 - volumetric shapes, orthographic perspective, angular view, axonometric projection
 - Low Poly: polygonal design, low-poly art style, geometric simplicity, minimalistic 3D, low-poly aesthetics, faceted surfaces, flat shading, simplified forms, low-poly landscapes, low-poly objects
 - Origami: in a paper folding style, origami artistry, folded paper designs, precision folding, simplicity, Japanese paper art
 - Biomechanical: a biomechanical character made of a mix of organic and robotic parts, cybernetics, exoskeleton, mechanical features
 - Steampunk: Victorian machinery, steampunk gadgets, brass and gears, steam-powered art, clockwork designs, industrial aesthetics, retro-futuristic, airship technology, steampunk fashion, vintage engineering, mechanical
 - Pirate Punk: as a pirate, intricate brass details, antique leather texture, mechanical, detailed gears, nautical, maritime, rugged, adventurous, weathered
 - Neon Punk: neon lights, cyberpunk neon, vibrant colours, urban cyberpunk, futuristic cityscape, neon punk aesthetics, glowing neon art, futuristic lighting, neon punk style
 - Fortnite: saturated (solid color background:1.5), [prompt], cartoony game character with exaggerated proportions, extravagant outfit, minimalist modelling, (low poly:0.5), (octane render:1.2)

Appendix II – Generation Information

a. Figure 3

Negative prompt: low-quality, watermark, deformed, distorted anatomy, poor artistry, NSFW, Cleavage, Nudity, Naked, explicit content, mutated features, extra limbs, extra fingers, ugly, missing body parts, disconnected elements, malformed, abnormal proportions, aberrant hands, aberrant feet, aberrant legs, aberrant fingers

Steps: 20, Sampler: Euler a, CFG scale: 7, Seed: 3844237688, Size: 1536x1024, Model hash: 70229e1d56, Model: juggernautXL_version5, Version: v1.6.0-2-g4afaaf8a

b. Figure 4

Steps: 20, Sampler: UniPC, CFG scale: 7, Seed: 92506533, Size: 640x1136, Model hash: 879db523c3, Model: dreamshaper.8

ControlNet 0: *Module: openpose_full, Model: control_v11p_sd15_openpose [cab727d4], Weight: 1, Resize Mode: Crop and Resize, Low Vram: False, Processor Res: 512, Guidance Start: 0, Guidance End: 1, Pixel Perfect: False, Control Mode: Balanced, Version: v1.6.0*

c. Figure 5

Negative prompt: Realistic, ultra realistic, 3D, symmetry

Steps: 30, Sampler: DPM++ 2M Karras, CFG scale: 7, Seed: 1457380060, Size: 1820x1024, Model hash: a40d817f46, Model: albedobaseXL_v13, Version: v1.7.0

d. Figure 6

Prompt (using dynamic prompt extension):

Hyper-realistic {ultra close-up — fisheye lens — Bird's-eye view — Depth of field — Low angled — Full body length — 18mm shot — 35mm shot — 85mm shot} photography, an austere old man standing on the street, highly detailed, 8k, masterpiece

Negative prompt: [default negative prompt]

Steps: 15, Sampler: Euler a, CFG scale: 7, Seed: 2471991075

e. Figure 8

Negative prompt: [default negative prompt]

Steps: 20, Sampler: Euler a, CFG scale: 7, Seed: 2302537629, Size: 1365x1024, Model hash: 0724518c6b, Model: juggernautXL_v7Rundiffusion, Version: v1.6.0-2-g4afaaf8a

f. Figure 9

Prompt (using dynamic prompt extension):

{5\$\$ Minimalist, intricate details — close-up shot — octane render, 3D rendering — heavy pistol, decorated with hand-painted drawing of an orange koi fish — photoreal, 4k, masterpiece}

Negative prompt: [default negative prompt]

Steps: 20, Sampler: Euler a, CFG scale: 7, Seed: 1480651971, Size: 1365x1024, Model hash: 0724518c6b, Model: juggernautXL_v7Rundiffusion, Version: v1.6.0-2-g4afaaf8a

g. Figure 10

Steps: 10, Sampler: DPM++ 2M Karras, CFG scale: 7, Seed: 4195241296, Size: 1024x1024, Model hash: ca4802bc3f, Model: juggernautXL_version45, Version: v1.6.0

h. Figure 11

Photorealistic image in *txt2img*:

Prompt: Photorealistic artwork of [character] from [game title] walking in a (Science-Fi:1.2) world, facing the camera, exoplanets, (futuristic city:1.5), alien technology, bright colours, (orange hue:0.5)

Negative prompt: French architecture, European buildings

Steps: 20, Sampler: DPM++ SDE, CFG scale: 7, Size: 1536x1024, Model hash: ca4802bc3f, Model: juggernautXL_version45, Version: v1.6.0

Cartoon image in *img2img*:

Prompt: Cartoon artwork of [character] from [game title] walking in a (Science-Fi:1.2), futuristic city, (exoplanets:1.2), alien technology, (orange hue:0.5), vibrant colours, textured patterns, Cartoon Art, illustrated

Negative prompt: drawing, painting, crayon, sketch, graphite, impressionist, noisy, blurry, soft, deformed, ugly. young. long neck. (cross eyed:1.5)

Steps: 20, Sampler: Euler a, CFG scale: 7, Size: 1843x1228, Model hash: 1b8fca3fee, Model: samaritan3dCartoon_v40SDXL, Denoising strength: 0.2, Version: v1.6.0

Manga image in *img2img*:

Prompt: Anime Studio artwork of [character] from [game title] walking in a (Science-Fi:1.2), futuristic city, (exoplanets:1.2), alien technology, (orange hue:0.5), Seinen

Negative prompt: text, weapons, gun

Steps: 20, Sampler: Euler a, CFG scale: 7, Size: 1536x1024, Model hash: c35e1054c0, Model: mistoonAnime.v20, Denoising strength: 0.7, Version: v1.6.0

Appendix III – Qualtrics Survey (Character Workflow Study)

Survey Description

Welcome to this survey examining the integration of stable diffusion in game development. The survey aims to gather feedback from individuals involved in game development, focusing on their experiences with stable diffusion and image generation. Your honest and thoughtful responses will greatly contribute to this research. This survey is conducted as part of a master's thesis research at HEC, University of Lausanne, which investigates the role of Generative AI (GenAI) in augmenting the work of concept artists. The research is centred on creating efficient workflows and user-friendly interfaces to streamline the use of GenAI, aiming to enhance creativity, the generation of varied artistic concepts, and to speed the design process. The objective is to make GenAI an accessible and practical tool for artists, minimising the technical complexities and the typically steep learning curve associated with it. This survey is anticipated to take approximately 5 minutes to complete.

Instructions

To participate in this survey, you will be guided through a four-step workflow for generating a character sheet. Detailed instructions for each step will be available within the workflow on the Automatic1111 web UI. Access to the workflow and the web UI link will be granted after you consent to data collection. Once you have completed the workflow, please continue to respond to the survey questions.

Data Collection Consent

Your responses will be kept anonymous and used solely for research purposes. The information gathered will contribute to a master's Thesis, to be shared with Ubisoft and the University of Lausanne. There's potential for this research to be adapted into a publication in the future. You maintain the right to withdraw from the survey at any stage. The images and any required Photoshop sketches generated during the workflow replication will be used for the thesis. All outputs will remain anonymous.

Consent Options:

- I consent
- I do not consent

Workflow Access Information

- Stable Diffusion web UI URL (Ubisoft internal network)
- The reference image to download and upload during Step 1 of the workflow
- The workflow to follow

General Questions

- **Q1:** Which of the following best describes your role at Ubisoft?
Artist, Developer/Programmer, Producer/Manager, Marketing, Game Designer
- **Q2:** What's your experience in the company?
0–3 years, 4–10 years, 11+ years

-
- **Q3:** How would you rate each statement about your experience with AI?
Scale: Strongly disagree to Strongly agree (1 to 5)
 - I regularly use AI-powered solutions in my everyday tasks
 - I have extensive experience using AI-driven tools for image generation
 - I have extensive experience generating images on Automatic1111 web-ui

Workflow Related Questions

- **Q4:** How would you rate each statement about your experience with the workflow?
Scale: Strongly disagree to Strongly agree (1 to 5)
 - The steps outlined in the workflow were clear
 - The steps outlined in the workflow were easy to follow
 - The web-ui is confusing due to numerous parameters
 - The web-ui is confusing due to the technical knowledge required to generate images
 - Completing the given task would have been more challenging without the workflow
 - I gained new techniques from using this workflow that I intend to apply in future tasks related to image generation
- **Q5:** What other challenges, if any, did you encounter while following the workflow for image generation?
- **Q6:** What suggestions, if any, would you like to see implemented in the workflow?

Figure 19: Qualtrics survey results part 1/2.

How would you rate each statement about your experience with AI? 5 ①

How would you rate each statement about your experience with AI?	Average	Minimum	Maximum	Count
I regularly use AI-powered solutions in my everyday tasks	4.20	3.00	5.00	5
I have extensive experience using AI-driven tools for image generation	4.00	2.00	5.00	5
I have extensive experience generating images on Automatic1111 web-ui	3.60	1.00	5.00	5

How would you rate each statement about your experience with the workflow? 6 ①

How would you rate each statement about your experience with the workflow?	Average	Minimum	Maximum	Count
The steps outlined in the workflow were clear	3.40	2.00	5.00	5
The steps outlined in the workflow were easy to follow	3.40	2.00	5.00	5
The web-ui is confusing due to numerous parameters	3.80	2.00	5.00	5
The web-ui is confusing due to the technical knowledge required to generate...	3.80	2.00	5.00	5
Completing the given task would have been more challenging without the work...	3.50	2.00	5.00	6
I gained new techniques from using this workflow that I intend to apply in...	3.20	2.00	4.00	5

What other challenges, if any, did you encounter while following the workflow for image generation? ①

Very hard to obtain a better result than the first image generated. The progress in image creation seems to decline steeply the more we persist or try to refine the image.

It doesn't work with everything; the character must be humanoid to have full access to the workflow. The sketch must be highly visible and even different from the rest of the image, so that the AI can understand and interpret the addition. There's not always consistency between the four poses.

Sometimes it's not clear for some parameters, it should be better specified

It was hard to reach the result I had in mind

What suggestions, if any, would you like to see implemented in the workflow? ①

A fragmented generation method might be interesting. Being able to see the progress of the image while it's generated on a zone of your choice might give you faster an idea if things are going in the right direction.

Perhaps add screenshots of the interface to help you understand where you need to go, especially when you're a beginner and know nothing about the platform. Or maybe a quick explanation of certain workflow functions such as denoise, to help you understand what you're doing and better apprehend the modification of settings.

Some screenshots would have helped to better follow each steps, or a guided video

less parameters, single prompt solution

Figure 20: Qualtrics survey results part 2/2.

Appendix IV – Semi-structured interview (ArtistUI study)

Workflow Integration and Efficiency

1. After testing ArtistUI, do you think its use allows concept artists to be more efficient and save time?
2. Can you describe specific cases in your work where this tool could help you do a task more easily or quickly (not necessarily related to the concept)? And independently of the last question, do you think you could integrate generative AI into your work in the future and how?

Creativity and Innovation

1. Does the use of this tool help in your creative process? Can it serve as a source of inspiration? Or lead you to new ideas that you might not have considered?

User Interface and Experience

1. How does ArtistUI influence your interaction with generative AI? Does it improve it by making the use of AI simpler (compared to using SD)?
2. Are there features that you would like to see in this UI? What aspects do you like and dislike and why?

Comparative Analysis

1. How do you compare your experience with AI tools to traditional concept art methods?
2. For you, what are the aspects of generative AI that you find particularly beneficial vs challenging?

Practicality and Accessibility

1. Do you think that guided use (workflow) and the interface (ArtistUI) can make generative AI more accessible to artists in video games, regardless of their level of familiarity with AI?
2. What would be the points to improve according to you to really integrate AI into game development pipelines in preproduction/production?

Future Perspectives

1. How do you envision the evolution of the role of generative AIs in the world of video games? Do you see potential in it? What would be the limitations according to you, and are you ready to adapt to this technology?

Anonymised answers

Question number	Participant number	Participant Answers
Q1	P1	Oui ! L'interface simple avec un prompt unique simplifie grandement le processus.
Q2		Oui, dans le cas de génération de variation d'item. Aujourd'hui créer des variations de couleurs et de texture pour un objet du jeu demande du temps sans grande valeur ajoutée. Cet outil pourrait permettre de générer une grande quantité de variations rapidement pour ensuite proposer une grande sélection d'image au directeur artistique et de décider lesquelles peuvent être utilisé en production.
Q3		Oui, pour moi il favorise l'idéation et résout le souci de la page blanche.
Q4		Oui la simplification de l'interface et la limitation des paramètres simplifie grandement la création de contenu avec l'IA, c'est beaucoup plus simple que quand j'essaie de faire la même tâche directement dans le webUI de SD. La limitation créative n'est pas apparente car obfusquée.
Q5		Oui, j'aimerais un moyen de contrôler la forme utilisée pour faire mes variations de textures. Et des conseils de prompting en "astuce" serait un vrai plus sur l'UI.
Q6		Le processus d'idéation est accéléré et permet de passer plus de temps sur de la création à forte valeur ajoutée.
Q7		L'idéation est bénéfique, et le control de l'output est challenging
Q8		Oui, c'est bien d'avoir un guide, mais c'est la limitation de paramètres obscure qui va surtout simplifier l'accès à l'IA pour tout le monde.
Q9		Ce qui est proposé avec cette interface s'inscrit directement dans points d'amélioration.
Q10		L'évolution de cette technologie est tellement rapide (déjà depuis 6 mois, on a beaucoup avancé) que je ne vois pas de limitation à son implémentation. Pour les artistes ils gagent du temps sur les tâches inutiles, mais le risque réel c'est de remplacer l'artiste (le directeur créatif pourrait suffire quand on aura complètement intégré l'IA générative). Il y a un grand potentiel avec les objets 3D, si les variations de textures se faisaient directement en text-to-3D, on aurait plus besoin de l'équipe chara ... typiquement sur un projet déjà publié qui est en "run down", où il faut qu'on laisse partir des gens mais que la création de contenu pour les items doit toujours être faite mais sans avoir besoin de beaucoup de monde sur le projet. Par Exemple quand on doit sortir des items par saisons.
Q1	P2	Evidemment, on est beaucoup plus guidé donc ça fait gagner du temps
Q2		Pour faire de la création de character, pour faire des moodboard, pour faire des enviro etc. Je m'en servais surtout pour chercher de l'inspiration pour quand je ne la trouve pas sur d'autres sites et dont je n'aurai pas forcément pensé

Q3		Oui, comme j'ai dit avant, ça serait l'utilité principale, et puis pour l'efficacité, d'avoir des propositions rapides qui sont assez cohérentes.
Q4		Il y a plus d'aisance, beaucoup moins de boutons, c'est très pratique
Q5		Pour faire jusqu'au bout, pour tout simplifier ça serait bien de pouvoir faire un sketch rapide directement dans l'UI pour ne pas avoir besoin d'ouvrir Photoshop. Les defaults c'est que pour l'instant on peut l'utiliser que pour un cas spécifique, ça serait bien de l'étendre à plus de possibilités, sinon l'UI est claire c'est bien pour les débutants en IA.
Q6		C'est beaucoup plus rapide mais par contre on est obligé de beaucoup retoucher pour avoir un résultat super précis, et c'est beaucoup plus technique en informatique, alors qu'avant le concept art c'est technique dans la façon de dessiner, avant je devais apprendre à maîtriser Photoshop et maintenant j'ai un outil en plus à maîtriser ce qui prend du temps.
Q7		Bénéfique l'inspiration et rapidité et challenging d'avoir un résultat intéressant dans la composition et tout et souvent on tombe facilement sur un résultat qui n'est pas assez varié ou ça peut donner des résultats pas du tout cohérents si le prompt n'est pas assez précis
Q8		Bien sûr
Q9		Moi j'utilise déjà l'IA générative dans mon travail de concept art au quotidien donc pour moi c'est déjà intégré dans mon workflow et mon processus de création
Q10		Oui il y a forcément du potentiel car c'est déjà là et ça peut que prendre de plus en plus de place. Je pense que ça va s'intégrer un peu dans tous les domaines du développement du jeu, mais on aura peut-être besoin de moins de personnes à ce moment-là, et dans les limitations je trouve que le travail d'un concept artiste est toujours beaucoup plus vivant, dans l'intention qu'il donne au résultat dans le rendering qu'il fait etc. L'IA rend de belles images mais ce n'est pas forcément parfaitement construit pour le moment.
Q1	P3	Les outils de Gen AI vont permettre de relever le niveau des concept artistes débutant, et permettront au senior d'arriver plus vite à des résultats qualitatifs. L'artistUI va dans la direction de la simplification d'utilisation et limite ainsi le workload mental nécessaire à l'utilisation de ce genre de technique
Q2		C'est très utile pour faire des illustrations de présentation, ou pour travailler rapidement sur du moodboard. L'idée n'étant pas d'être très précis dans ce genre de cas, mais de dégrossir des directions.
Q3		Même réponse que la dernière question.
Q4		La complexité est cachée, donc c'est plus simple à utiliser et plus rapide.
Q5		Je voudrais que ça ne soit pas un prototype mais un produit fini à mettre en prod

Q6		Ces outils permettent à n'importe qui d'obtenir un résultat qualitatif relativement satisfaisant.
Q7		Cet outil génère beaucoup d'inquiétude et d'interrogation auprès des artistes, c'est une vraie disruption technologique, tout comme la photographie ou la mocap avant. Le niveau bas des artistes va monter drastiquement, c'est très positif. Il faut cependant rester attentif aux évolutions rapides et se préparer au changement
Q8		Oui
Q9		La production de contenu est décuplée, il faut prévoir des systèmes d'évaluation plus en adéquation avec cette quantité de matière.
Q10		Tout comme le procédural a pris une part importante dans la production sans remplacer les artistes en place, l'IA va venir en supplément du reste. Il y a un énorme potentiel, en particulier sur les UGC, mais les problématiques de cout seront le vrai obstacle pour ce genre de déploiement
Q1	P4	Oui, faire un chara avec l'artistUI m'a pris environ 15 min en comptant le sketch sur Photoshop, si j'avais dû tout dessiner moi-même ça m'aurait pris environ 2 heures
Q2		J'aimerais bien que cet outil soit adapté pour m'aider à faire des environ plus rapidement, et je pense que si on développe ça un peu plus, je serais ravi de l'intégrer à mon travail au quotidien comme un outil en plus de mon workflow et pas comme une manière de le remplacer complètement
Q3		Oui, en fait ça va devenir comme un outil de recherche, au lieu d'aller sur internet pour trouver des références je peux les générer avec de l'IA, ça change la manière de faire mais fondamentalement ça sert aussi à faire de l'idéation, mais en plus rapide
Q4		Oui
Q5		J'aimerais bien un moyen de cliquer sur un bouton qui me donne des styles différents pour ne pas faire que des images réalistes, et je trouve qu'on pourrait encore plus automatiser le character workflow en enlevant des étapes. Avec SD sur le webUI, je passe beaucoup plus de temps à chercher où sont les paramètres et vérifier que je fais les choses correctement, je me trompe souvent et dois retourner en arrière, ça prend beaucoup de temps, là au moins c'est direct et simple
Q6		C'est très différent et il me faudra un temps d'adaptation mais j'aime beaucoup utiliser des IA génératives
Q7		On a déjà parlé des bénéfices, le défi c'est toujours de contrôler le résultat, de trouver le bon prompt qui marche bien etc.
Q8		Oui, c'est sûr.
Q9		Il faudrait laisser le temps aux personnes de s'adapter, il y en a beaucoup qui n'apprécient pas les IA dans les jeux et je comprends leurs raisons, mais avec un peu d'adaptation ça devrait aller mieux, il faut leur prouver que ça marche bien

Q10		Bien-sûr, je vois aussi du potentiel dans la génération de vidéos, de script, d'objet 3D etc. Je pense que ça peut s'adapter dans beaucoup de domaine de la création d'un jeu
Q1	P5	I think it can be useful in certain situations; as for speeding up the process, it seems a bit early.
Q2		First and foremost, I find it useful in generating inspirational images, in mixing and bringing together ideas that we might not necessarily associate.
Q3		As I already said, it can be useful for free association, brainstorming and juxtaposition of let's say an object with a non-characteristic style, or a location, a time, etc with unexpected styles, colours, etc.
Q4		I think we need an ArtistUI, a model trainer to help us (artists) think like the "machine" and make the UI evolve into a more controllable tool.
Q5		I would like to see that a recognition logic and application of certain rules once the object/fragment is recognized or assigned a name. For now, that works to some degree for faces and little more. I would also like to see some development in constructing an image in 3 dimensions. If we limit the tool to generating pixels in a 2-dimensional space, we will not be able to progress.
Q6		Very remote from how we work traditionally. It requires a different way of thinking, but the principles of image construction remain the same.
Q7		There is a lot of "surface" generated in a very short time, many things that would take longer to render by hand and a certain "freshness", unbiased take. Things that do not work and we fight a lot with, are refining an image in a certain direction, some basic lack of logic that even 2 years old would know to avoid, too much detail, too much contrast in the images, too much saturation sometimes, not being able to fine tune concepts as these last ones, etc. There is a lot of stuff that does not work for now.
Q8		Of course.
Q9		Developing models that are custom made for a project or for a task. Having artists involved in the training and model developing.
Q10		3d and interface. Obviously, I see a lot of potential. The first limit I can see if that AI is based on flat images and thus cannot deal with entities, yet. It deals with pixels and that to me is dead-end. Yes, I am ready to learn how to use AI and ready to answer to as many huge questions you might have in the future.
Q1	P6	A ce moment précis, les IA avec un grand contrôle sont assez austère. L'application d'une UI plus intuitive fait forcément gagner un temps non négligeable.
Q2		De manière générale dans son avancement présent, l'IA est trop imparfaite pour servir de travail fini mais il peut offrir des pistes intéressante. Ca serait dans un premier temps comme ça qu'il serait utilisé dans mon cas, dans un travail préliminaire de recherches de plusieurs pistes rapidement.
Q3		Comme dit plus c'est un outils intéressant dans les premières phases de travail, afin de dégager rapidement différentes directions et aussi de voir rapidement ce qui marche ou non.

Q4		Totalement, à l'instar d'une planche tendance ou de références c'est un outil qui peut être puissant mais qui dans son état actuel, encore une fois, mérite d'être couplé avec des recherches de références classiques.
Q5		ArtistUI offre un outils fonctionnel et compréhensible rapidement par la plupart des gens. Donc il fluidifie grandement son utilisation au plus grand nombre.
Q6		Peut-être dans un second temps après une première génération, avoir des options « entonnoire » pour affiner les étapes suivantes.
Q7		Sa simplicité de prise en main.
Q8		La génération par IA à un aspect quasi immédiat (une fois les outils pris en main) qui permet pour le moment beaucoup de rendement pour une qualité relative, alors que le concept art traditionnel permet dans ses étapes, de cibler plus rapidement ce qu'on veut mais avec un résultat plus long dans l'exécution. Je ne les mettrai pas en opposition mais plus en combinaisons comme je le disais précédemment la génération par IA est un outils assez puissant pour le travail de recherches préliminaire.
Q9		La rapidité d'itérations qui va devoir dans le futur se combiner à un rendu plus précis et propre dans les détails.
Q10		Oui, complètement. Avec une interface tel que artistUI, tout le monde peut prendre en main cet outils sans aucunes difficultés.

Appendix V – Figure

Figure 26: Full figure of: Exploring All Combinations of Sequential Orders for the Five Prompting Categories

Appendix VI – Extensions and models

Extensions To install extensions, open A1111 WebUI, navigate to the “Extension” tab, then click on “Install from URL” and paste the extension’s GitHub repository URL and press “Install”, then back to the extension tab and click on “Apply and restart UI”.

- ControlNet, URL: <https://github.com/lllyasviel/ControlNet>
- After installing the extension, download the pre-trained ControlNet models from this URL: <https://huggingface.co/lllyasviel/ControlNet-v1-1/tree/main>
Download the files that ends with .pth (at least the depth, lineart and scribble models)

Place the downloaded model in the following folder location: “extensions/sd-web- ui/ControlNet/models” within the Stable Diffusion folder.

- Regional Prompter, URL: <https://github.com/hako-mikan/sd-webui-regional-prompter>
- Infinite Image Browsing, URL: <https://github.com/zanllp/sd-webui-infinite-image-browsing>
- Dynamic Prompt, URL: <https://github.com/adiyal/sd-dynamic-prompts>

Models To install model checkpoints, download the file (they can be found at civitai.com or Hugging Face) and place the models in the following folder location: “models/Stable-diffusion”, then close and run the .bat file to run Automatic1111 WebUI.

- Realistic vision, URL: <https://civitai.com/models/4201/realistic-vision-v60-b1>